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Editor's Choice

Low-Voltage Controlled Coercivity in Nanocrystalline Fe-Ni Films by Magneto-Ionic Effects

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Received: 19 September 2025 | **Revised:** 10 November 2025 | **Accepted:** 17 November 2025

Keywords: coercivity | Fe-Ni | magnetic films | magnetoelectric | magneto-ionic | nanocrystalline | voltage control of magnetism

ABSTRACT

Magneto-ionic control of metal oxide/metal films provides a pathway to voltage-tunable magnetoelectronic devices with high energy efficiency. So far, magneto-ionic research mainly focuses on Co-based films, while Fe-Ni alloy films, despite their high industrial relevance, have not been studied systematically. In this work, a combined in situ Kerr microscopy and electrochemical analysis demonstrates magneto-ionic control of coercivity in nanocrystalline Fe-Ni alloy films across the whole compositional range. The required voltage is low (~ 1 V) and decreases with increasing Ni content, presumably relating to the nobler nature of Ni versus Fe. For Fe-rich alloys, a large voltage-induced change of coercivity and remanence is connected to an oxide-to-metal transformation, reducing domain wall pinning. For intermediate compositions, the magneto-ionic effects are largest. Here, the potential induces a moderate increase, followed by a drastic reversible decrease in coercivity by $\sim -90\%$. This behavior is attributed to the enhanced electrochemical reactivity of ultrafine grains and the heterogeneous oxide present on mixed bcc/fcc Fe-Ni films. For Ni-rich films, the magneto-ionic effects are small, but voltage-induced magnetic softening is still achieved. The study introduces Fe-Ni films as a promising magneto-ionic material platform and highlights the potential of tailored, defect-rich microstructures for boosting magneto-ionic performance.

1 | Introduction

Magneto-ionics offer a transformative approach to tune magnetic properties via electrochemical reactions and/or ion migration, providing a route to non-volatile switching by low voltages and ambient conditions. Magneto-ionic control is achieved through voltage-gating of a magnetic material via a solid or liquid electrolyte. This approach has immense potential for energy-efficient memory technologies, sensing and actuating applications, and neuromorphic computing [1–4].

The vast majority of magneto-ionic studies to date focus on Co-based thin films, with oxygen or hydrogen as the active

ionic species [5–8]. In recent years, the field expanded toward magneto-ionic control of complex multilayers [9], nanoporous [10] as well as micron-size [11] materials and toward using other ions (N^{3-} , Li^+ , OH^-) [12–14]. Magneto-ionic control of diverse magnetic properties, including magnetic anisotropy [15–18], coercivity [15, 16, 19–21], magnetization [22, 23], exchange bias [24–26], magnetoresistance [27], RKKY coupling [10, 12, 28], and complex magnetic textures [29–31] has been demonstrated.

Despite their high industrial relevance, Fe-Ni alloys have not been systematically studied with regard to magneto-ionic effects so far. Fe-Ni alloys are valued for their high magnetic permeability, low coercivity, and tunable magnetic anisotropy, which are crucial for

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magnetic and spintronic applications such as sensors, spin valve heterostructures, and microwave components. Precise control of magnetic states is vital in these areas. Permalloy, typically referring to Fe₂₀Ni₈₀, is a prominent alloy composition that exhibits extremely low coercivity and high permeability. Wood et al. [32], provide a first indication of magneto-ionic effects in 5 nm Fe₂₀Ni₈₀ films gated via an ionic liquid. They observe a decrease in coercivity and magnetic moment under an oxidation potential and attribute these effects to oxidation of the Fe₂₀Ni₈₀ film and an associated layer thickness change.

While magneto-ionic effects in the Fe-Ni alloy system have not been researched further and in detail yet, magneto-ionic mechanisms occurring in single Fe films are well-understood. The magneto-ionic effect in FeO_x/Fe films upon electrolytic gating in alkaline solution relies on the reversible reduction and re-oxidation of the surface oxide layer [33]. Reversible, low-voltage control of anisotropy and coercivity [19], exchange bias [25], and ON-OFF-switching of magnetization [23] are demonstrated in FeO_x/Fe films with this mechanism. From this perspective, magneto-ionic control of Fe-Ni films should also be within reach.

The present study aims to systematically explore magneto-ionic effects in Fe-Ni alloy films. For this purpose, nanocrystalline Fe-Ni films are prepared by electrodeposition. This method is particularly advantageous due to the rapid processing and operation under ambient conditions. We chose to investigate films with thicknesses of 100 to 200 nm because this range allows us to probe magneto-ionic effects beyond the ultra-thin regime while ensuring uniform and homogeneous film deposition. The alloy composition is varied from Fe to Ni in steps of about 10 at.%, in order to cover the full compositional range in sufficient detail. Thickness, roughness and microstructure of the films are closely monitored to evaluate their possible influence on the magneto-ionic performance. The change of the magnetic properties upon electrolytic gating is studied via in situ magneto-optical Kerr (MOKE) magnetometry and microscopy. In parallel, the electrochemical reactions are analyzed in detail by cyclic voltammetry and current density transients, as well as in situ Raman spectroscopy. The focus lies on reaching a fundamental understanding of the complex interdependencies between composition, microstructure, electrochemical reactions, and resulting potential-dependent magnetic properties.

2 | Results and Discussion

2.1 | Nanocrystalline Fe-Ni Alloys as Starting Material for Magneto-Ionics

All films are prepared by potentiostatic electrodeposition for 60 s from the same base electrolyte to provide comparability. Different alloy compositions are obtained by adjusting the ion concentration of the metal salts in the electrolyte (see Experimental Section, Table S1 and Figure S1). In addition to the alloy composition measured by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), we monitored thickness, roughness, structure, and microstructure of the deposited films as potential additional influence factors for magneto-ionic effects.

Figure 1a shows that the average film thicknesses are in the range from 100 to 200 nm. A representative profilometer scan is provided in Figure S2a. Figure 1b shows the root mean-square (RMS) roughness of the films as derived from atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements. The pure iron film is noticeably rougher, with an RMS roughness an order of magnitude greater than that for the Fe-Ni and Ni films. This is presumably connected to the electrolyte solution, which is commonly used for Fe-Ni alloys, but not optimized for Fe deposition. For Ni contents of 23 and 32 at.%, RMS roughness decreases to about 8 and 5 nm, respectively. Films with more than 40 at.% Ni and pure Ni films are smooth and exhibit a similar RMS roughness of 3–4 nm. Examples of an AFM image and a cross-sectional transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image are provided in Figure S2b,c, confirming the smooth film surface.

The microstructure of the films is characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (see Figure S3). The lattice constants derived from XRD are displayed in Figure 1c.

Fe and Fe-rich Fe-Ni films with <40 at.% Ni exhibit body-centered cubic (bcc) structure, while Ni and Ni-rich films with >63 at.% Ni have face-centered cubic (fcc) crystal structure. For near-equiatomic composition, the analysis of the lattice parameter from XRD is not fully reliable due to the broad and overlapping peaks, and therefore those values are given in brackets in Figure 1c. The extracted non-linear dependence of the fcc lattice constant on the Fe content agrees with earlier studies on electrodeposited Fe-Ni films [34], and may be related to an anomalously large magnetovolume effect in fcc Fe-Ni alloys [35]. For intermediate Ni contents, a two-phase mixture of fcc and bcc crystal structures is detected. Such a metastable mixed fcc/bcc region is commonly reported for Fe-Ni films [36, 37]. High-resolution TEM (HR-TEM) and associated Fast Fourier Transformation analysis of an Fe₅₆Ni₄₄ cross-sectional sample also reveals a mixture of fcc and bcc phases (Figure S4a,b). All films exhibit nanosized grains, evidenced by significant broadening of the XRD peaks (see Figure S3). We calculated the coherence length from the XRD measurements as an estimate for the average grain size. Figure 1d shows that this estimated grain size minimizes to average values of about 5–10 nm in the two-phase region, which agrees with earlier studies on electrodeposited Fe-Ni alloys [36]. The nanocrystalline microstructure is also observed in HR-TEM images in which the nanograins appear darker when they are oriented along a low-index zone relative to the electron beam (see Figures S2c and S4a). These nanograins are visible as bright regions in a high-angle annular dark-field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) image of a similar area (Figure 1e). The HAADF-STEM image shows the position (yellow box) where electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) was carried out at each scanning point to obtain elemental maps of Fe, Ni, and O (blue, pink, and green in Figure 1e) across the entire film at a width of 88 nm and a pixel size of 11 nm. These elemental maps, as well as the ones determined from EDX mapping (Figure S4c,d) reveal that Fe and Ni are evenly distributed throughout the film, evidencing a homogeneous deposition process. At the surface of the film, the oxygen content increases due to the native oxide layer, which forms during storage in ambient air conditions after the electrodeposition process. From the EELS elemental maps (see line profiles in Figure S4c) a native oxide layer thickness of less

FIGURE 1 | Morphological, microstructural, and magnetic properties of electrodeposited Fe-Ni films with different compositions. (a) average film thickness h measured by profilometry, (b) RMS roughness from AFM analysis, (c) lattice constants of bcc and fcc phase, a_{bcc} and a_{fcc} , respectively, and (d) estimated grain size of bcc and fcc phase, d_{bcc} and d_{fcc} , respectively. Lattice constants and estimated grain size are extracted from XRD diagrams (Figure S3). In (c), the dashed black and red lines present the lattice constants for bcc Fe(110) and fcc Ni(111), taken from ICSD-1953192 and ICSD-646088, respectively. The values in brackets in (c) are estimates due to broad peaks and peak overlap in the XRD diagrams. (e) Cross-sectional HAADF-STEM image and elemental mapping of Fe, Ni, and O obtained by EELS in a $\text{Fe}_{56}\text{Ni}_{44}$ film. The area for the EELS mapping is marked in yellow in the TEM image. (f) In-plane MOKE magnetic hysteresis loops for films of different composition and (g) coercivity for all films as a function of composition.

than 10 nm (pixel size) can be approximated for the $\text{Fe}_{56}\text{Ni}_{44}$ sample.

Figure 1f shows representative magnetization curves for Fe-rich, near-equiatomic, Ni-rich, and pure Ni films, measured by longitudinal magneto-optical Kerr effect (MOKE) magnetometry. All films are magnetically isotropic in the film plane (Figure S5a). The hysteresis loops exhibit a rounded shape at the beginning of magnetization reversal, indicating rotational magnetization processes, and subsequent fast switching by domain wall motion. The low susceptibility of the virgin curve (Figure S5b) indicates that domain wall pinning is the dominant mechanism for magnetization reversal. Coercivity values derived from MOKE loops for all films are displayed in Figure 1g in dependence of composition. The Fe film possesses the highest coercivity of all studied films, which is presumably connected to the high surface roughness in conjunction with the magnetocrystalline anisotropy of Fe. Coercivity decreases with increasing Ni content up to $\text{Fe}_{19}\text{Ni}_{81}$, where a minimum coercivity (0.5 mT) is reached due to the expected vanishing magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant and magnetostriction close to this near-permalloy composition [38]. For Ni films, a higher coercivity is measured again, which is as expected due to the increased magnetocrystalline and magnetoelastic anisotropy, compared to near-permalloy composition.

The similar thickness and roughness achieved in the compositional film series are favorable for studying the influence of the composition of Fe-Ni films on magneto-ionic effects. Only the Fe films exhibit a significantly higher roughness compared to the Ni and Fe-Ni films, and therefore, we discarded them for the following magneto-ionic study. With regard to the microstructure, all Fe-Ni and Ni films exhibit nanocrystallinity, with the

smallest grains occurring in the two-phase region at intermediate compositions. Since these microstructural changes cannot be avoided, we will consider them as an additional influence factor for the interpretation of magneto-ionic effects later on.

2.2 | Magnitude and Onset Potential of Magneto-Ionic Changes Vary with Fe-Ni Composition

In order to investigate magneto-ionic effects for our Fe-Ni film series, we apply electrolytic gating in an alkaline electrolyte solution. With this electrolyte, large magneto-ionic effects have been previously reported for FeO_x/Fe films [24]. We use in situ MOKE magnetometry and microscopy to simultaneously monitor voltage-induced electrochemical reactions and corresponding changes of the magnetic properties of the Fe-Ni films. MOKE measurements are inherently surface-sensitive, probing only the near-surface region of the sample due to the optical penetration depth of the incident light, which is expected to be approximately 20 nm in our setup. Figure 2a shows a scheme of the combination of the electrochemical cell and the MOKE microscope, further details can be found in the Experimental Section.

In the in situ MOKE setup, we first measure a magnetic hysteresis after immersion in the electrolyte, at the open circuit potential (OCP). Then we apply successively more negative (cathodic) potentials E to the Fe-Ni and Ni films to induce magneto-ionic effects. The starting potentials of -0.9 and -1.0 $\text{V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ are sufficiently more positive than the potentials for possible surface reduction reactions. Each potential is held for 60 s and during this time, a complete hysteresis loop is measured.

FIGURE 2 | Magneto-ionic effects for Fe-Ni films with different compositions measured by in situ MOKE microscopy. (a) Scheme of the in situ MOKE microscopy setup with a three-electrode electrochemical cell and the Fe-Ni films connected as the working electrode. (b) Coercivity and Kerr intensity difference δI for the different Fe-Ni films as extracted from in situ in-plane MOKE hysteresis loops in the electrolyte solution during application of successively more negative potentials (black and orange dots, respectively). The H_C value at the OCP state is added for comparison (blue dots). The dashed grey areas mark the potential regions in which MOKE measurements are not possible due to hydrogen evolution. (c) MOKE microscopy images showing the magnetic domains close to the coercive field for an $\text{Fe}_{55}\text{Ni}_{45}$ film in pristine state and in the electrolyte at $-1.24 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$.

Figure 2b displays the changes of coercivity and Kerr intensity difference δI of the in situ MOKE hysteresis loops in dependence of the applied potential for eight films with different compositions. δI is monitored here, because it may give indications of the change in saturation magnetization when voltage-induced reduction of surface oxide to metal occurs [19]. For Fe-Ni films with high Fe content ($\text{Fe}_{85}\text{Ni}_{15}$ and $\text{Fe}_{77}\text{Ni}_{23}$), a drastic decrease in coercivity, accompanied by a strong increase in δI , is observed for potentials below $-1.24 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$. For the intermediate compositions of $\text{Fe}_{68}\text{Ni}_{32}$, $\text{Fe}_{66}\text{Ni}_{34}$, and $\text{Fe}_{55}\text{Ni}_{45}$, a strong voltage-induced decrease of H_C is similarly found. However, for these films, the coercivity drop is preceded by an increase in coercivity of about 13%–19%. In parallel to the coercivity changes, a strong increase in δI is again observed. For Ni-rich films ($\text{Fe}_{34}\text{Ni}_{66}$ and $\text{Fe}_{19}\text{Ni}_{81}$) and the Ni film, a voltage-induced decrease of coercivity with a smaller relative magnitude of the effect than for the films with higher Fe content is found (please note the different scales on the left axis in Figure 2b). For Ni films, only a slight decrease in coercivity

is noticed below $-1.00 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$. For both, Ni-rich and Ni films, changes in δI are negligible. The comparison of the curves in Figure 2b also reveals that the potentials at which the voltage-induced changes occur become more positive with increasing Ni content.

In a subsequent experiment with the $\text{Fe}_{55}\text{Ni}_{45}$ sample, we confirmed that the significant voltage-induced decrease in H_C is both reproducible and reversible (Figure S6a). On another sample, we found that the voltage-induced increase and subsequent decrease of coercivity also occur over time when a potential of $-1.22 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ is directly applied, instead of the step-wise reduction procedure (Figure S6b). In this experiment, we observe partly non-volatile behavior and the voltage-induced decrease of coercivity becomes larger when a negative potential is applied for the second time. This indicates that alterations in the reduction and oxidation protocol could be used to achieve different magnetic states. Evaluation of the hystereses in Figure S6b, in combination

with the magnetic field scan rate, reveals that after repeated switching the magneto-ionic effect occurs within 17 s or faster. The time resolution is limited by our MOKE measurement setup.

For the Fe₅₅Ni₄₅ film, Figure 2c exemplarily shows magnetic domain images captured during magnetization reversal in the pristine state and during voltage-gating at $-1.24 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$. While in the pristine state, fine elongated domains are visible, much larger domains are observed for the low-coercivity state at the reduction potential.

2.3 | Composition-Dependent Electrochemical Reactions Correlate to Magneto-Ionic Effects

To investigate correlations between electrochemical reduction reactions and the magneto-ionic response for the different Fe-Ni compositions, we conducted detailed electrochemical analysis in conjunction with the in situ MOKE microscopy study.

For all film compositions, we performed cyclic voltammograms (CV), where the current density j is monitored upon potential cycling between OCP and $-1.4 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$. Figure 3a shows representative first-cycle CVs for Fe, Fe₅₄Ni₄₆, and Ni films. For the Fe film, the CV is as expected from previous works [39]. The forward scan shows a distinct peak of the cathodic current density j at about $-1.30 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$ (see inset in Figure 3a), which is assigned to the reduction of Fe²⁺ species to Fe: $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 + 8 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow 3 \text{ Fe} + 4 \text{ O}^{2-}$ [40]. The subsequent further increase of $|j|$ is due to the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), which proceeds via the reduction of water molecules in alkaline solution: $2 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 2 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + 2 \text{ OH}^-$. In the CV of the Fe₅₄Ni₄₆ film, the increase in $|j|$ in the cathodic scan is much stronger and starts at more positive potentials than for the Fe film. A distinct $|j|$ -peak is not observed, which indicates that surface oxide reduction overlaps with enhanced HER in this case. Furthermore, a larger j -peak occurs in the anodic scan, which points at a more significant re-oxidation of the Fe₅₄Ni₄₆ film than for the Fe films (see also enlargement in Figure S7a). In the cathodic scan of the Ni film, $|j|$ starts to increase at even more positive potentials than for the Fe₅₄Ni₄₆ film and again, a peak cannot be resolved. The further increase of $|j|$ on the Ni film toward more negative potentials, indicative of HER, is intermediate between the j -response of the Fe and the Fe₅₄Ni₄₆ films.

For magneto-ionic effects, HER is a parasitic side reaction, which limits the accessible potential range in cathodic direction. At the same time, hydrogen absorption, which can occur in parallel to HER, may induce hydrogen-based magneto-ionic mechanisms [6, 16, 41]. The enhanced HER on Ni and especially Fe-Ni films, as compared to the single Fe films, can be ascribed to the highly catalytic nature of Ni/Ni-oxide for HER, which is known to improve further for mixed Fe-Ni/oxide surfaces [42]. The lower catalytic activity of Fe/Fe-oxide for HER readily explains that magneto-ionic effects are measurable down to lower cathodic potentials for Fe-rich films (see Figure 2b). However, the observed shift of the starting potential of magneto-ionic effects to more positive values for films with increasing Ni content counterbalances the simultaneous, undesired enhancement of HER.

For energy efficiency, the onset voltage for magneto-ionic effects should be as small as possible. Thus, a shift of the potential for underlying electrochemical reduction processes to more positive values is desirable. For a full picture, we have extracted the onset potentials for electrochemical reduction reactions ($E_{\text{EC,onset}}$) from CVs for all film compositions. Figure 3b shows that, indeed, $E_{\text{EC,onset}}$ increases almost linearly with increasing Ni content from about $-1.15 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$ for Fe films to $-1.05 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$ for Ni films. From simple thermodynamic considerations, the more positive standard potential of Ni/Ni²⁺ compared to Fe/Fe²⁺ could readily explain this shift. However, we cannot provide an unambiguous origin at this point, as kinetic factors may also play a role, and as we cannot safely discriminate between surface metal oxide reduction and water reduction in the CV. Importantly, the comparison in Figure 3b shows that a very similar trend is observed for the onset potentials for the magneto-ionic effects ($E_{\text{MI,onset}}$) observed by in situ Kerr microscopy. This confirms that the magneto-ionic effects are coupled to electrochemical reactions, and that the film composition has a direct influence on the required gating voltage.

In Figure 3c we show that, besides the change of the onset voltage, also the maximum achievable relative magneto-ionic effect on coercivity (extracted from the data shown in Figure 2b) strongly varies throughout the compositional series. Large effects with a maximum decrease of coercivity of around -70% are obtained for Fe-rich films. For intermediate compositions, even larger magneto-ionic effects on coercivity are obtained, reaching -90% for the Fe₅₅Ni₄₅ film. The bottom panel in Figure 3c reveals that large magneto-ionic effects on coercivity are always accompanied by huge relative changes of the Kerr intensity differences, which indicate a strong increase in the saturation magnetization at the film surface. This observation is a first indication that for Fe-rich films, an electrochemically induced transformation of a weakly magnetic surface metal-oxide to ferromagnetic metal is the primary origin of the magneto-ionic effects, similar to previous findings for thin Fe films [19]. Beyond intermediate Fe-Ni composition, the maximum relative magneto-ionic effects strongly decrease for increasing Ni content, but still reach -9% for Ni films.

The maximum magneto-ionic effects presented in Figure 3c are obtained at different potentials, as the potential-dependency of the electrochemical reduction reactions changes within the compositional series. To evaluate the magneto-ionic performance in dependence of the Ni content under similar conditions, we present a comparison of the magneto-ionic effect at a fixed potential of $-1.24 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$ in Figure 3d. At this potential, HER is not yet interfering with the measurement for all samples. The upper panel in Figure 3d shows that in this case large relative effects on coercivity are only achieved for intermediate compositions. In contrast to Figure 3c, the effects are small for both Fe-rich and Ni-rich films. This is because for the Fe-rich films, the potential is not negative enough yet (see Figure 2b) to induce the electrochemical reduction reaction for this film composition. The associated transferred charge $|q|$ extracted from the simultaneously measured current transients (see Figure S7b) is plotted in the bottom panel of Figure 3d. Up to $\sim 80\%$ Ni, the transferred charge follows the same trend as the magnitude of the magneto-ionic effect in dependence of composition, again confirming that the magneto-ionic effects are linked to the

FIGURE 3 | Correlating magneto-ionic effects and electrochemical reactions in Ni, Fe, and Fe-Ni films with different compositions. (a) First cycle of cyclic voltammograms of Fe, Fe₅₄Ni₄₆, and Ni films in 1 M KOH solution. (b) Comparison of the onset potentials for magneto-ionic effects ($E_{MI,onset}$) revealed by in situ MOKE magnetometry and those for electrochemical reduction reactions ($E_{EC,onset}$) extracted from CVs in dependence of the Fe-Ni film composition. (c) Maximum voltage-induced relative change of H_C (top panel) achieved for different compositions, defined as: $\Delta H_{C,max} = [(H_{C,E,min} - H_{C,OCP})/H_{C,OCP}] \cdot 100\%$, where $H_{C,E,min}$ is the minimum H_C achieved during the voltage-routine displayed in Figure 2b, and $H_{C,OCP}$ is H_C in OCP state. The potential values, at which the maximum effect is achieved, is given in grey font. The bottom panel shows the corresponding relative changes in δI , defined as: $\Delta(\delta I) = [(\delta I_E - \delta I_{Ref})/\delta I_{Ref}] \cdot 100\%$, where δI_E is δI at the potential of the minimum H_C state (see top panel) and δI_{Ref} is δI during the first reduction step, respectively. (d) Relative change of H_C achieved at $E = -1.24$ V_{Ag/AgCl} in dependence of composition (top panel), defined as: $\Delta H_{C,-1.24V} = [(H_{C,-1.24V} - H_{C,OCP})/H_{C,OCP}] \cdot 100\%$, where $H_{C,-1.24V}$ is H_C at -1.24 V_{Ag/AgCl}. The lower panel displays the corresponding charge $|q|$ transferred during the reduction procedure until the end of the potential step at -1.24 V_{Ag/AgCl}.

electrochemical reactions. Only for the Ni film, the transferred charge is higher than expected, considering the small magneto-ionic effect. This may be connected to the early start of the reduction reactions on Ni (-1.05 V_{Ag/AgCl}), making HER possible for an extended time prior to -1.24 V_{Ag/AgCl}. HER is not expected to contribute to the magneto-ionic effect, but it adds to the transferred charge.

So far, the results revealed that for all films in the Fe-Ni series, voltage-control of coercivity can be achieved by electrolytic gating. The magneto-ionic effects are found to be coupled to electrochemical reactions, which may be surface oxide reduction and/or hydrogen absorption. The absolute value of the required voltage decreases with increasing Ni content, but the magnitude of the voltage-induced coercivity change is much stronger for Fe-rich as opposed to Ni-rich films. The largest magneto-ionic effects are achieved for films with near-equiatomic compositions, where the electrochemical reaction rate is also enhanced.

2.4 | Discussion of the Impact of Microstructure on Magneto-Ionic Effects in the Fe-Ni Film Series

To understand the cause of the compositional dependency of magneto-ionic effects, we provide a more detailed investigation and discussion on the underlying electrochemical reactions and on the influence of the microstructure in the following. We divide our discussion into three parts: First, we discuss magneto-ionic mechanisms for films on the Fe-rich side, then for those close to equiatomic composition, and finally for Ni-rich films.

Representative for Fe-rich films, the voltage-dependent coercivity evolution of a Fe₇₇Ni₂₃ film is shown in Figure 4a, together with selected hysteresis loops. Starting from a H_C of 10.4 mT at the OCP, H_C starts to decrease below -1.18 V_{Ag/AgCl} and finally reaches the lowest value of 3.6 mT at -1.28 V_{Ag/AgCl}. This corresponds to a relative decrease of H_C of 65%. The inset shows that in addition to changes in coercivity, the shape of the hysteresis loop also changes upon reduction. While a rounded loop is present

FIGURE 4 | Understanding different magneto-ionic effects in the Fe-Ni film series considering surface oxide reduction on varying microstructures. a) Evolution of coercivity for a $\text{Fe}_{77}\text{Ni}_{23}$ film when successively applying more negative potentials in 1 M KOH solution. b) In situ Raman spectra for a $\text{Fe}_{82}\text{Ni}_{18}$ film in 1 M KOH solution at OCP and during step-wise reduction from -1.00 to $-1.20 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$. Evolution of coercivity for c) an $\text{Fe}_{54}\text{Ni}_{46}$ and d) a Ni film when successively applying more negative potentials in 1 M KOH solution. Insets in a), c), and d) depict hysteresis loops at OCP and at characteristic reduction potentials. The dashed lines mark the coercivity of the pristine state. The sketches at the bottom of a), c), and d) visualize the proposed mechanism based on surface oxide reduction on the different microstructures consisting of a) bcc, c) mixed fcc/bcc, and d) fcc grains.

at OCP, the hysteresis loop at $-1.27 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ is more rectangular with a significantly higher remanence. This shows that not only a voltage-induced magnetic softening, but also a voltage-controlled magnetization without the assistance of a magnetic field might be within reach.

For the Fe-rich films, we propose that surface oxide reduction leading to reduced domain wall pinning is the underlying mechanism for the coercivity drop, in analogy to previous findings for Fe films [19]. The observed strong increase in the Kerr intensity difference and the electrochemical analysis both agree with surface oxide reduction. Furthermore, hydrogen absorption in Fe and Fe-rich alloys with bcc structure is negligible ($5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mol} \cdot \text{H} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$ solubility in Fe) [43], and thus is most likely not relevant here as magneto-ionic mechanism. In order to confirm the oxide-based mechanism, we performed in situ Raman measurements. Figure 4b shows the in situ Raman spectra

of an $\text{Fe}_{82}\text{Ni}_{18}$ film in OCP state and for applied potentials of -1.00 , -1.18 , and $-1.20 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$. A significant change of peaks (1) and (2) is observed upon voltage application, while peaks (3) and (4) at higher wavenumbers remain largely unchanged. The small peak (3) at 1063 cm^{-1} is likely due to carbonate contamination (CO_3^{2-}) [44], and the broad peak (4) at 1636 cm^{-1} is assigned to the O–H bending mode of adsorbed water [45]. Peak (1) at 521 cm^{-1} and peak (2) at 673 cm^{-1} indicate surface oxides. Because of the limited number of peaks in the spectrum together with their broadness, we cannot assign them unambiguously. Peak (2) agrees well with the dominant A_{1g} mode of magnetite (Fe_3O_4), which is reported at 672 cm^{-1} [46], and which is also observed for sputtered Fe films at OCP in alkaline solution [19]. The dominant A_{1g} mode of nanocrystalline NiFe_2O_4 (680 cm^{-1}) [47] is also close to this peak position. The broader peak (1) cannot be readily assigned to a specific oxide. Magnetite (T_{1u} , $538\text{--}554 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) [46], maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, E_g ,

511 cm^{-1}) [46], and α -/ β -Ni(OH)₂ (510–530 cm^{-1}) [48] exhibit modes close to the position of this peak. Importantly, under the application of reduction potentials from -1.00 to -1.20 V_{Ag/AgCl}, both peaks (1) and (2) weaken and almost disappear eventually. This is consistent with a potential-induced oxide reduction. We thus conclude that the magneto-ionic mechanism leading to the drastic decrease of coercivity for Fe-rich Fe-Ni films relies on surface oxide reduction. This mechanism is visualized in a sketch at the bottom of Figure 4a.

Surface oxide reduction may also explain the significant voltage-induced change in remanence observed for the Fe₇₇Ni₂₃ film. One possibility is that the magnetic field applied during the in situ MOKE measurement influences the morphology of the newly-formed Fe at the surface, leading to a change in anisotropy [49]. Another possible scenario is that the reduction of grain boundary oxides increases magnetic exchange-coupling between the nano-sized grains, resulting in remanence enhancement [50]. Further investigations are required for a fundamental understanding here.

During the electrolytic gating of Fe-Ni films with intermediate compositions an increase in H_C prior to the expected decrease in H_C upon stepwise reduction is observed (see Figure 2b). Figure 4c highlights this unusual H_C evolution for the Fe₅₄Ni₄₆ film and shows four corresponding hysteresis loops in the inset. The coercivity of the natively oxidized state in the electrolyte at OCP is 5.4 mT. The onset of the magneto-ionic effect occurs at -1.12 V_{Ag/AgCl}, with an increase in H_C reaching a maximum of 6.4 mT at -1.18 V_{Ag/AgCl}. Further reduction steps lead to a decrease in H_C to 0.56 mT at -1.24 V_{Ag/AgCl}, corresponding to a relative change of -90% , with the OCP state as reference. Between the maximum and minimum H_C , a transition via a double-hysteresis shape is observed at -1.22 V_{Ag/AgCl}.

We propose that the potential-induced intermediate coercivity increase is related to the specific two-phase microstructure present at near-equiatom compositions (see Figure 1c,d). In situ Raman could not resolve surface oxide peaks in this case, which may be connected to a low crystallinity of the oxide formed on films with extremely small grains (see Figure 1d). Obtaining a Raman signal in situ is challenging for a thin oxide layer, because of the low Raman intensity [51]. Genuzio et al. [52]. Recently evaluated X-ray absorption spectra of phase-separated Fe-Ni films and found that the oxidation rate is much faster on bcc grains than on fcc grains, yielding considerably thicker oxide layers on bcc than on fcc grains. We can thus expect a heterogeneous oxide layer on our mixed bcc/fcc films after native oxidation. The potential-induced reduction of such a heterogeneous surface oxide would not proceed homogeneously across the film surface. We hypothesize that the oxide on bcc grains requires more negative potentials and/or longer times for reduction than the oxide on fcc grains for two reasons: First, a thicker oxide requires longer to be reduced than a thinner oxide, especially as the reduction process starts at the metal/oxide interface [40]. Second, from thermodynamic considerations and confirmed by our electrochemical analysis (Figure 3b), the oxide reduction on an Fe-rich (bcc) surface should start at more negative potentials than on a Ni-rich (fcc) surface. A heterogeneous oxide reduction process would lead to an intermediate state, where the internal roughness of the metal-

oxide interface is increased. This is visualized in the second panel in the sketch in Figure 4c. Such an increased internal roughness could be a possible origin of the enhanced coercivity in the intermediate potentials. The occurrence of the double step hysteresis loop after the high coercivity state would also agree with a stepwise reduction process, where one portion of the oxide is reduced more easily than the second portion. When the potential becomes even more negative, a thicker oxide on the bcc grains can also be reduced, explaining the low-coercivity state analogous to the Fe and Fe-rich films. The observation of larger domains (Figure 3c) in the reduced state agrees with the proposed metal oxide-to-metal transformation reducing the domain wall pinning sites. Previous work also found magnetic domain refinement when transforming an oxide-free Fe-Ni surface to an oxidized surface [52].

The magnetic domain evolution during magnetization reversal can give additional insights. Therefore, we display the domain images during magnetization reversal for the intermediate state in comparison to those of pristine, high-coercivity, and low-coercivity states in Figure S8. The comparison indicates that an inhomogeneous surface is present in the intermediate state: One part of the surface is already in a low-coercivity state, where large domains move at low applied magnetic fields, while the other part reverses via the motion of fine, elongated domains at higher applied magnetic fields, comparable to the behavior in the pristine state.

The achievement of the maximum magneto-ionic effects at intermediate compositions (Figure 3c,d) can also relate to the extremely fine-grained two-phase microstructure. The small grain size of around 5–10 nm (Figure 1d) goes along with a high density of grain and phase boundaries, which are the most active regions for oxidation [52] and electrochemical reactions [53]. A high reaction rate for these films, for both reduction and oxidation processes, is evidenced in the large transferred charge upon stepwise reduction (Figure 3d) and in the significantly larger electrochemical oxidation current in the anodic scan in the CV (Figure S7a). We propose that the comparably large amount of oxide at the film surface and in the grain boundaries, which can be reduced upon electrolytic gating, explains the highest magneto-ionic effects achieved in films with near-equiatom composition.

Repeated switching experiments for films with near-equiatom composition show that coercivity fully recovers upon voltage switch-off, indicating that restoration of the oxide layer occurs in the electrolyte at OCP state (Figure S6a). The results obtained during repeated stepwise reduction confirm that the large magneto-ionic effects are reversible. With a different switching routine, partially non-volatile behavior is observed (Figure S6b), indicating that optimization of the magneto-ionic routines may enable voltage-programmable states. Furthermore, results in Figure S6b evidence that the coercivity decrease occurs more rapidly when a very negative potential is directly applied for a second time, compared to the stepwise reduction routine. This finding could be explained by faster kinetics of the electrochemical surface oxide reduction caused by higher absolute overpotentials, but also points at the importance of sample history and training procedures.

For Ni-rich films, magneto-ionic effects evolve at more positive potentials, but the magnitude of the magneto-ionic effects on coercivity and Kerr intensity difference decreases and eventually almost vanishes toward pure Ni (see Figure 2b). The behavior for a Ni film is shown in Figure 4d. From the coercivity at OCP (9.3 mT), coercivity starts to decrease at $-1.00 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ to about 8.5 mT at $-1.08 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$. Both hysteresis loops are depicted in the inset. From the microstructural analysis we only observe the fcc phase (see Figure 1c). Thus, a comparably thin and homogenous surface oxide is expected [52], which can be reduced at more positive potentials than for films with higher Fe content (see sketch at the bottom of Figure 4d). In combination with an increasing grain size (see Figure 1d) this scenario can explain the weakening of the magneto-ionic effects with increasing Ni-content on the Ni-rich side of the Fe-Ni film series. The reduced activity with regard to surface metal oxidation on Ni is also obvious from the almost negligible anodic peak in Figure S7a and the negligible change of the Kerr intensity difference (Figure 2b). It should be noted, that for fcc Fe-Ni and Ni films, hydrogen absorption may become an additional magneto-ionic mechanism [54, 55]. In a recent in situ magnetometry study, we show that a small decrease of magnetic moment in Ni films upon application of a reduction potential relates to hydrogen absorption [41]. Such small magnetic moment changes, however, cannot be resolved with in situ MOKE measurements. Even though magneto-ionic effects on the Ni-rich side are weaker than for Fe-rich films, they may still become relevant for tuning coercivity of, e.g., permalloy as an industrially relevant material.

3 | Conclusion

To investigate the impact of composition on magneto-ionic mechanisms in the Fe-Ni system, we performed a systematic study of electrolytic gating of nanocrystalline, electrodeposited Fe-Ni alloy films. Thickness and roughness are comparable throughout the film series, except for the Fe films. While the Fe-rich and Ni-rich films exhibit bcc and fcc structures, respectively, a two-phase bcc/fcc microstructure with extremely small grains is present for near-equiatomic compositions.

For all compositions, in situ MOKE microscopy revealed that low-voltage-induced changes in coercivity are achieved. However, the magnitude of the effects strongly varies across the compositional series. For Fe-rich films, large effects up to 70% decrease in coercivity and an increase in remanence are found, which are assigned to surface oxide reduction on the basis of electrochemical and in situ Raman analysis. For intermediate compositions, an even larger voltage-induced decrease of coercivity up to 90% could be achieved, which is preceded by a moderate increase of coercivity. For these films, electrochemical analysis reveals a significantly higher electrochemical activity, which we attribute to the extremely fine-grained microstructure. We discuss the particular intermediate potential-induced enhancement of coercivity with a stepwise electrochemical reduction process of a heterogeneous surface oxide on the mixed bcc/fcc microstructure. We hypothesize that an associated increase in internal roughness can temporarily enhance domain wall pinning. Finally, Ni-rich and Ni films exhibit much weaker magneto-ionic effects than near-equiatomic and Fe-rich films. We relate this finding mainly

to the thinner surface oxide formed on less-reactive fcc Ni and Fe-Ni [51].

Our study reveals that microstructural details, e.g., grain size, phase composition, or type of oxide, are key influence factors for the magneto-ionic performance in the Fe-Ni system. A reduction in grain size, causing an increase in reactive defect sites for electrochemical reactions, is proposed as a general, promising route toward enhancing magneto-ionic effects. This strategy should be transferable to numerous other magneto-ionic systems, which rely on the reaction rate of electrochemical reactions. The introduction of defective sites by, e.g., ion bombardment or specific growth procedures, could serve the same purpose. One recent example in this direction is the control of magneto-ionic performance of Co_3O_4 films by ion bombardment [56]. However, a large gate voltage (-50 V) is required for the transformation from Co_3O_4 to Co in this study. For the $\text{FeNiO}_x/\text{Fe-Ni}$ system, which is tunable by low voltage ($\sim 1 \text{ V}$) in our study, the design of the oxide by the fabrication procedure or microstructural optimization seems a viable route to tailoring the magnitude and potential-dependency of magneto-ionic effects in the future. Selective reduction of different oxide phases on laterally structured materials may for example, pave the way to voltage-programmable domain wall traps for domain wall logic devices.

In general, we expect similar magneto-ionic effects for Fe-Ni films prepared by physical deposition methods. For sputtered and natively oxidized Fe films magneto-ionic control of coercivity with a comparable oxygen-based mechanism has already been demonstrated [19]. Future studies could clarify whether and how differences in the microstructure, roughness, and specifics of the native oxide layer in sputtered films compared to electrodeposited ones affect the magnitude and the compositional dependency of the magneto-ionic effect.

To fundamentally understand how alloy composition influences the magneto-ionic effect, we employed a step-wise reduction approach. We find a direct correlation between the onset potential of magneto-ionic effects and the composition of the films. For a higher Ni content, increasingly less negative potentials are required, which means that the voltage required to induce magneto-ionic effects decreases. We can directly explain this from the difference in standard potentials, i.e., the less reactive (more noble) nature of Ni as opposed to Fe. We conclude that considering thermodynamics for optimizing gate voltage requirements is important for optimizing energy-efficient magneto-ionic devices in the future. In addition, faster magneto-ionic effects with switching times in the range of seconds are achieved by repeated direct switching between a very negative reduction potential and the off state, as opposed to a stepwise reduction procedure. This highlights the importance of kinetics and initial training effects.

Importantly, this work introduces Fe-Ni alloy films as a novel, promising magneto-ionic material platform. We demonstrate low-voltage-controlled coercivity for all compositions, and for specific compositions also voltage-controlled remanence. Even for the permalloy composition with high industrial relevance, significant voltage-induced magnetic softening is achieved. Within the Fe-Ni alloy system, the highest magneto-ionic effects of up to 90% become possible for near-equiatomic compositions. With

this systematic demonstration of magneto-ionic mechanisms in FeNi_x/Fe-Ni films in a broad compositional range, we open a research field toward the development of voltage-tunable Fe-Ni-based materials for extremely energy-efficient magnetic sensing, actuation, and computing applications.

4 | Experimental Section/Methods

4.1 | Fabrication of the Fe-Ni Films

Fe-Ni films were fabricated on Si/SiO₂/Cr/Au substrates via electrochemical deposition. The substrates were prepared by DC magnetron sputtering of Au/Cr layers on thermally oxidized Si(100) wafer pieces. The sputter conditions were equal to those described in previous work [19]. The electrochemical cell used for Fe-Ni film deposition employed the Cr/Au coated wafer substrate as the working electrode (WE) at the bottom of the cell, a platinum sheet as the counter electrode, and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode. The area of the WE is 0.385 cm², limited by an O-ring. For deposition, a Watts bath-type electrolyte (pH = 3) containing NiCl₂ · 6 H₂O (Supelco, 99%), NiSO₄ · 6 H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich, 99%), FeSO₄ · 7 H₂O (Grüssing GmbH, 99.5%), H₃BO₃ (408 mmol), and ascorbic acid (17 mmol) was used. The alloy composition was adjusted via the concentration of the metal salts, specified in Table S1. The Fe²⁺-containing electrolytes were freshly prepared and used within one day, after purging with N₂ gas for ~30 min. Deionized water (Thermo Scientific Barnstead GenPure Pro, 0.057–0.060 μS·cm⁻¹, 1–2 ppb TOC) was used for the preparation of the electrolyte solution, cleaning, and in any further in situ experiments. The electrolyte volume in the deposition cell was approximately 10 mL. All electrodepositions were carried out under potentiostatic control at -1.1 V_{SCE} for 60 s using a BioLogic SP-50 potentiostat. After electrodeposition, the samples were promptly removed from the electrolyte solution (within less than 10 s), rinsed with deionized water, dried under N₂ gas flow and stored under ambient conditions.

4.2 | Characterization of Film Composition and Microstructure

Scanning electron microscopy and EDX were conducted by an FEI Nova NanoSEM and a XFlash Detector 5010 (Bruker Nano GmbH) using 12 kV, 1000x magnification, and 8 min for each EDX mapping. HR-TEM imaging and STEM-EELS elemental mapping were performed on the cross-section of the Fe₅₆Ni₄₄ film using an aberration-corrected Titan [3] 80–300 TEM instrument (ThermoFisher Company, USA). The microscope was operated at 300 kV electron acceleration voltage and a Gatan Tridiem imaging filter (GIF) was used to record the EEL spectra. EELS quantification was carried out using the “EELS Analysis Offline” software package within Gatan DigitalMicrograph.

To determine the thickness of the films, height profiles were acquired using contact profilometry (Bruker, DektakXT). For each sample, three line-scans were performed, each spanning 8 mm and traversing through the center of the deposit. For all scans, baseline correction and smoothing were applied. The baseline was determined by selecting the level of the substrate as

reference points. Vertical linear fits were then applied to both the deposit surface profile and the profile of the substrate. The height for each line scan was determined by the difference between these two fits. The average height is the average value of the heights of the three line scans.

AFM was carried out using a Nano Wizard II from JPK Instruments in intermittent mode. The AFM topological images were edited with Gwyddion 2.61 freeware by 1) leveling the data by mean plane subtraction, 2) polynomial alignment of the row, and 3) correction of horizontal scars. Roughness was obtained via the statistics tool.

XRD was performed on representative films deposited from each electrolyte solution (see Section S1) using a Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer (9 kW rotating anode, Cu K_α radiation) in parallel beam using a two-bounce Ge(220) monochromator. The coherence length as an estimate for the grain size is calculated using the SCHERRER equation:

$$d = \frac{0.94\lambda}{\Delta H(2\theta)\cos\theta} \quad (1)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the used X-ray beam and $\Delta H(2\theta)$ is the full width at half maximum and θ the Bragg angle.

4.3 | Characterization of Magnetic Properties

Magnetic characterization of the as-deposited films was performed using MOKE magnetometry and microscopy (evico magnetics GmbH), with selective sensitivity to pure in-plane magnetization using the longitudinal Kerr effect and utilizing an in-plane electromagnet. Magnetic domain images and MOKE hysteresis loops were recorded using an LD Plan-NEOFLUAR objective from Zeiss with 20x magnification. Background image subtraction, utilizing an image from the saturated state, was employed to enhance the domain contrast. Corrections for drift and the FARADAY effect originating from the lens were applied to the recorded hysteresis loop.

4.4 | In Situ MOKE Microscopy Cell Setup and Electrochemical Procedure for Characterization of Magneto-Ionic Effects

To investigate magneto-ionic effects and corresponding electrochemical reactions, a custom-built three-electrode in situ cell (see Figure 2b) was employed in combination with a MOKE microscope. Further details on the cell can be found in previous work [24]. The electrodeposited Fe-Ni samples functioned as WE, while a platinum wire served as the counter electrode. A Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode, was placed in an external container and connected to the in situ cell reservoir by a hose filled with the electrolyte, ensuring ionic conductivity. The electrolyte used to induce magneto-ionic effects consisted of 1 M KOH (Fisher Chemical) aqueous solution. The electrolyte volume in the in situ cell was 200 μL. An O-ring restricts the working electrode area to 0.385 cm². A BioLogic SP-50 potentiostat was used to control the magneto-ionic experiments. All voltages quoted in this work related to magneto-ionic measurements represent the potential

difference between the Fe-Ni film and the Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode. Hysteresis loops were measured by MOKE microscopy as described in the previous paragraph, but this time focusing on the films through a cover glass and the electrolyte.

CV measurements were performed in the in situ cell with a scan rate of $10 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. For in situ magneto-ionic characterization the following routine was applied to each sample: First, a hysteresis loop was measured after addition of the electrolyte in OCP state. Then, starting at -0.90 or $-1.00 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$, successively more negative potentials were applied in steps of 20 mV up to $E = -1.24 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$. Below $-1.24 \text{ V}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$, a potential step size of 10 mV was used to capture more details of the magneto-ionic effects. The measurements were continued down to the most possible negative potential, before bubbles due to HER impeded the MOKE measurement. Each potential was applied for one minute, during which a hysteresis loop was recorded. The current was constantly monitored (see example in Figure S7b). Experimental details for the magneto-ionic switching routines presented in the Supporting Information are presented in the caption of Figure S6.

4.5 | In Situ Raman Spectroscopy

In situ Raman measurements were carried out using an UMPlan-FLN 20XW Olympus water immersion objective in a T64000 triple spectrometer (Jobin Yvon Horiba), equipped with a diffraction grid of $600 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mm}^{-1}$ and a 532 nm excitation wavelength of a Torus 532 laser (Laser Quantum). A three-electrode electrochemical cell with a Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode and a Pt wire as counter electrode was used, and the potential was applied to the Fe-Ni films as WE via a BioLogic SP-50 potentiostat.

Acknowledgements

Co-funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation, project number 499361641) and the European Union (ERC, ACTIONS, 101125178). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. D.W. acknowledges financial support by the Collaborative Research Center SFB 1143 (project-id 247310070). We acknowledge C. Tegenkamp and D. Dentel (TU Chemnitz) for providing the opportunity to perform SEM/EDX measurements and O. Hellwig (TU Chemnitz) for access to XRD measurements. We thank M. Gößler (TU Chemnitz) for discussion and help with MOKE measurements, D. Quint (TU Chemnitz) for discussion and help with the three-electrode in situ cell, and A. Pöhl for preparation of the FIB lamella.

Funding

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (499361641), European Union (ERC, ACTIONS, 101125178), Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (247310070).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17699113>.

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Supporting Information

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